

BOUNDEDNESS OF THE HILBERT TRANSFORM ON WEIGHTED LORENTZ SPACES

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ABSTRACT. We study the boundedness of the Hilbert transform H and the Hilbert maximal operator H^* on weighted Lorentz spaces $\Lambda_u^p(w)$. We start by giving several necessary conditions that, in particular, lead us to the complete characterization of the weak-type boundedness of both H and H^* , whenever $u \in A_1$. For the strong-type case, we also get the characterization of both operators when $p > 1$. Applications to the case of Lorentz spaces $L^{p,q}(u)$ are presented.

1. INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

In 1972, Muckenhoupt [15] gave the complete characterization of the boundedness of the Hardy-Littlewood maximal operator M on weighted Lebesgue spaces $L^p(u)$, with $p > 1$. Recall that

$$Mf(x) = \sup_{x \in I} \frac{1}{|I|} \int_I |f(y)| dy,$$

where I is an interval of the real line and the supremum is considered over all intervals containing $x \in \mathbb{R}$ and, for a positive locally integrable function u in \mathbb{R} , $L^p(u)$ is defined as the set of all Lebesgue measurable functions f such that

$$\|f\|_{L^p(u)} = \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}} |f(x)|^p u(x) dx \right)^{1/p} < \infty.$$

The characterization [15] was given in terms of the A_p condition:

$$\sup_I \left(\frac{1}{|I|} \int_I u(x) dx \right) \left(\frac{1}{|I|} \int_I u^{-1/(p-1)}(x) dx \right)^{p-1} < \infty.$$

Similarly, if we consider the weak-type spaces $L^{p,\infty}(u)$ defined by

$$\|f\|_{L^{p,\infty}(u)} = \sup_{t>0} f_u^*(t) t^{1/p} < \infty,$$

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where f_u^* is the decreasing rearrangement of f with respect to u (see [5]), it was also proved in [15] that, if $p > 1$,

$$M : L^p(u) \longrightarrow L^p(u) \quad \Longleftrightarrow \quad M : L^p(u) \longrightarrow L^{p,\infty}(u),$$

and that

$$M : L^1(u) \longrightarrow L^{1,\infty}(u)$$

is bounded if and only if $u \in A_1$; that is,

$$Mu(x) \leq Cu(x), \quad a.e. \ x \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Some years later, in [2], Ariño and Muckenhoupt gave the complete characterization of the boundedness of M on some weighted Lorentz spaces. These spaces were defined by Lorentz in [13] and [14] as follows: let $\mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R})$ be the class of Lebesgue measurable functions on \mathbb{R} . Then

$$\Lambda_u^p(w) = \left\{ f \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}) : \|f\|_{\Lambda_u^p(w)} = \left(\int_0^\infty (f_u^*(t))^p w(t) dt \right)^{1/p} < \infty \right\},$$

and

$$\Lambda_u^{p,\infty}(w) = \left\{ f \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}) : \|f\|_{\Lambda_u^{p,\infty}(w)} = \sup_{t>0} W^{1/p}(t) f_u^*(t) < \infty \right\},$$

with u and w positive locally integrable functions in \mathbb{R} and $(0, \infty)$ respectively (these functions will be called weights from now on), and

$$W(r) = \int_0^r w(s) ds.$$

The weighted Lorentz spaces were deeply studied in [7]. We list now some facts that will be important for our purposes.

Proposition 1.1.

(a) $\Lambda_u^p(w)$ and $\Lambda_u^{p,\infty}(w)$ are quasi-normed spaces if and only if w satisfies the Δ_2 condition ($w \in \Delta_2$); that is, $W(2r) \lesssim W(r)$, $r > 0$.

(b) Assume that $u \notin L^1(\mathbb{R})$, $w \notin L^1(\mathbb{R}^+)$ and $w \in \Delta_2$. If $|g_n| \leq |f|$, $f \in \Lambda_u^p(w)$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} g_n = g$ almost everywhere, then $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|g - g_n\|_{\Lambda_u^p(w)} = 0$.

(c) If $w \in \Delta_2$, the class of simple functions with support in a set of finite measure,

$$\mathcal{S}_0(u) = \left\{ f \in \mathcal{M} : \text{card}(f(\mathbb{R})) < \infty, u(\{f \neq 0\}) < \infty \right\}$$

is dense in $\Lambda_u^p(w)$.

The result proved in [2] (see also, for example, [6], [8]) corresponds to the case $u = 1$ and is the following:

$$M : \Lambda^p(w) \longrightarrow \Lambda^p(w)$$

is bounded if and only if $w \in B_p$; that is,

$$\int_r^\infty \left(\frac{r}{t}\right)^p w(t) dt \lesssim \int_0^r w(s) ds,$$

for every $r > 0$. Moreover, if $p > 1$ this condition also characterizes the weak-type boundedness:

$$M : \Lambda^p(w) \longrightarrow \Lambda^{p,\infty}(w)$$

and, if $p \leq 1$, the weak-type boundedness holds if and only if w is p quasi-concave; that is, there exists $C > 0$ such that, for every $0 < r < t < \infty$,

$$\frac{W(t)}{t^p} \leq C \frac{W(r)}{r^p}.$$

Some important facts about these classes of weights are the following [2, 7, 17]: by definition, we say that $w \in B_{p,\infty}$ if and only if the Hardy operator

$$Pf(t) = \frac{1}{t} \int_0^t f(s) ds,$$

satisfies that

$$P : L_{\text{dec}}^p(w) \rightarrow L^{p,\infty}(w)$$

is bounded, where $L_{\text{dec}}^p(w)$ is the set of decreasing functions on $L^p(w)$. Then:

- (i) If $p > 1$, $B_p = B_{p,\infty}$.
- (ii) For every $p \leq 1$, $w \in B_{p,\infty}$ if and only if w is p quasi-concave.
- (iii) For every $p > 0$, $w \in B_p$ if and only if

$$P : L_{\text{dec}}^p(w) \rightarrow L^p(w)$$

is bounded.

Recently, the complete characterization of the boundedness of

$$M : \Lambda_u^p(w) \longrightarrow \Lambda_u^p(w)$$

was proved in [7] by means of the following condition: there exists $q \in (0, p)$ such that, for every finite family of intervals $(I_j)_{j=1}^J$, and every family of measurable sets $(S_j)_{j=1}^J$, with $S_j \subset I_j$, for every j , we have that

$$(1.1) \quad \frac{W\left(u\left(\bigcup_{j=1}^J I_j\right)\right)}{W\left(u\left(\bigcup_{j=1}^J S_j\right)\right)} \lesssim \max_{1 \leq j \leq J} \left(\frac{|I_j|}{|S_j|}\right)^q,$$

where, for a measurable set E , we write $u(E)$ to denote $\int_E u(x) dx$, and as usual, we use the symbol $A \lesssim B$ to indicate that there exists a universal constant $C > 0$, independent of all important parameters, such that $A \leq CB$ and $A \approx B$ indicates that both $A \lesssim B$ and $B \lesssim A$

hold. This is the standard notation that we will also use throughout this paper.

Similar to the case of the maximal operator M , there is also a corresponding theory for the Hilbert transform (or, more generally, for singular integral operators). The Hilbert transform is defined by:

$$Hf(x) = \frac{1}{\pi} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{|x-y|>\varepsilon} \frac{f(y)}{x-y} dy,$$

whenever this limit exists almost everywhere. We know that this is the case for simple functions

$$\mathcal{S}(u) = \left\{ f \in \mathcal{M} : \text{card}(f(\mathbb{R})) < \infty \right\},$$

or for \mathcal{C}^∞ functions with compact support, \mathcal{C}_c^∞ . We shall also consider the Hilbert maximal operator

$$H^* f(x) = \frac{1}{\pi} \sup_{\varepsilon > 0} \left| \int_{|x-y|>\varepsilon} \frac{f(y)}{x-y} dy \right|.$$

Our main goal is to study the boundedness of the Hilbert transform and of the Hilbert maximal operator on weighted Lorentz spaces

$$(1.2) \quad H, H^* : \Lambda_u^p(w) \longrightarrow \Lambda_u^p(w)$$

and also its weak version $H, H^* : \Lambda_u^p(w) \longrightarrow \Lambda_u^{p,\infty}(w)$. We shall give first some general necessary conditions and obtain, as a consequence, the characterization of (1.2) and its weak-type version under the hypothesis that $u \in A_1$.

As in the case of the Hardy-Littlewood maximal operator, the cases $w = 1$ and $u = 1$ are already known:

(i) If $w = 1$, (1.2) is equivalent to the fact that

$$H : L^p(u) \rightarrow L^p(u)$$

is bounded and this problem was completely solved by Hunt, Muckenhoupt, and Wheeden in [12]. An alternative proof was provided in [10] by Coifman and Fefferman and the condition is that $u \in A_p$, if $p > 1$. This property also characterizes the weak-type boundedness:

$$H, H^* : L^p(u) \rightarrow L^{p,\infty}(u),$$

and, if $p = 1$,

$$H, H^* : L^1(u) \rightarrow L^{1,\infty}(u)$$

is bounded if and only if $u \in A_1$. Moreover, it is known that if

$$(1.3) \quad H, H^* : L^p(u) \rightarrow L^{p,\infty}(u)$$

is bounded, then necessarily $p \geq 1$; that is, there are no weights u for which the boundedness holds for some $p < 1$. This follows from the

fact that (1.3) implies that, for every measurable set $E \subset I$,

$$\frac{u(I)}{u(E)} \leq C \left(\frac{|I|}{|E|} \right)^p$$

and if $p < 1$, the Lebesgue differentiation theorem would imply that $u = 0$ (see [12]).

(ii) On the other hand, if $u = 1$, the characterization of (1.2) is equivalent to the boundedness of

$$H, H^* : \Lambda^p(w) \longrightarrow \Lambda^p(w),$$

given by Sawyer in [18]. A simplified description of the class of weights that characterizes the above boundedness is $B_p \cap B_\infty^*$, where a weight $w \in B_\infty^*$ if

$$(1.4) \quad \int_0^r \frac{1}{t} \int_0^t w(s) ds dt \lesssim \int_0^r w(s) ds,$$

for all $r > 0$ (see [16]).

If we consider the weak-type boundedness

$$H, H^* : \Lambda^p(w) \longrightarrow \Lambda^{p,\infty}(w),$$

then the complete characterization is $w \in B_{p,\infty} \cap B_\infty^*$.

The paper is organized as follows: in Section 2, we shall present several necessary conditions to have the weak-type boundedness of H on $\Lambda_u^p(w)$. As a consequence, we prove in Section 3 two of the main results of this paper, Theorems 3.5 and 3.6, which give the characterization of the boundedness of H under the assumption that $u \in A_1$, namely, for every $p > 0$,

$$H : \Lambda_u^p(w) \rightarrow \Lambda_u^{p,\infty}(w) \iff w \in B_{p,\infty} \cap B_\infty^*,$$

and, if $p > 1$,

$$H : \Lambda_u^p(w) \rightarrow \Lambda_u^p(w) \iff w \in B_p \cap B_\infty^*.$$

Moreover, this characterization also works for the Hilbert maximal operator H^* (see Remark 3.8).

In order to avoid trivial cases, we shall assume that the weights u and w satisfy the following condition:

$$W \left(\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} u(x) dx \right) > 0.$$

Finally, we recall the definition of the associated space of $\Lambda_u^p(w)$ (see [5]) since it will appear later on.

Definition 1.2. The *associate space* of $\Lambda_u^p(w)$ is defined as the set of all measurable functions g such that

$$\|g\|_{(\Lambda_u^p(w))'} := \sup_{f \in \Lambda_u^p(w)} \frac{\left| \int_{\mathbb{R}} f(x)g(x)u(x)dx \right|}{\|f\|_{\Lambda_u^p(w)}} < \infty.$$

In [7], these spaces were given in terms of the Lorentz spaces Γ defined as follows.

Definition 1.3. If $0 < p < \infty$,

$$\Gamma_u^p(w) = \left\{ f \in \mathcal{M} : \|f\|_{\Gamma_u^p(w)} = \left(\int_0^\infty (f_u^{**}(t))^p w(t) dt \right)^{1/p} < \infty \right\},$$

where $f_u^{**}(t) = Pf_u^*(t)$, and

$$\Gamma_u^{p,\infty}(w) = \left\{ f \in \mathcal{M} : \|f\|_{\Gamma_u^{p,\infty}(w)} = \sup_{t>0} W^{1/p}(t) f_u^{**}(t) < \infty \right\}.$$

Theorem 1.4. [7] *The associate spaces of the Lorentz spaces are described as follows:*

(i) *If $p \leq 1$, then*

$$(\Lambda_u^p(w))' = \Gamma_u^{1,\infty}(\tilde{w}),$$

where $\tilde{W}(t) = tW^{-1/p}(t)$, $t > 0$. (ii) *If $1 < p < \infty$ and $w \notin L^1(0, \infty)$,*

$$(\Lambda_u^p(w))' = \Gamma_u^{p'}(v),$$

where $v(t) = t^{p'}W^{-p'}(t)w(t)$, $t > 0$.

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2. NECESSARY CONDITIONS

We start by considering some necessary conditions for the boundedness of the Hilbert transform.

Theorem 2.1. *Let $0 < p < \infty$ and let us assume that the operator H is well defined on $\Lambda_u^p(w)$ and that*

$$H : \Lambda_u^p(w) \longrightarrow \Lambda_u^{p,\infty}(w)$$

is bounded. Then, the following conditions hold:

(a) *$u \notin L^1(\mathbb{R})$ and $w \notin L^1(\mathbb{R}^+)$.*

(b) *For every interval I and every measurable set E such that $E \subset I$, we have that*

$$(2.1) \quad \frac{W(u(I))}{W(u(E))} \lesssim \left(\frac{|I|}{|E|} \right)^p.$$

In particular, $W \circ u$ satisfies the doubling property; that is, $W(u(2I)) \lesssim W(u(I))$, for all intervals $I \subset \mathbb{R}$, where $2I$ denotes the interval with the same center than I and double size-length.

(c) W is p quasi-concave.

(d) For every interval I ,

$$(2.2) \quad \|u^{-1}\chi_I\|_{(\Lambda_u^p(w))'} \|\chi_I\|_{\Lambda_u^p(w)} \lesssim |I|.$$

Remark 2.2. One could think that, in the case $p > 1$, the boundedness $H : \Lambda_u^p(w) \rightarrow \Lambda_u^p(w)$ holds if both the boundedness $H : L^p(u) \rightarrow L^p(u)$ (characterized by the condition A_p) and the boundedness $H : \Lambda^p(w) \rightarrow \Lambda^p(w)$ (characterized by $w \in B_p \cap B_\infty^*$) hold. However, we prove with the following examples of u and w that, in general, the conditions $u \in A_p$ and $w \in B_p \cap B_\infty^*$ are not sufficient for the boundedness of H on $\Lambda_u^p(w)$, for $p > 1$.

If the Hilbert transform is bounded on $\Lambda_u^p(w)$, with $u(x) = |x|^k$ and $w(t) = t^l$ with $k, l > -1$, then (2.1) implies that

$$(2.3) \quad (k+1)(l+1) \leq p.$$

But, if we choose p and $k = l$ such that $\sqrt{p} < k+1 < p$, then $u(x) = |x|^k \in A_p$ and $w(t) = t^k \in B_p \cap B_\infty^*$. However, such $k = l > -1$ do not satisfy (2.3), since $p < (k+1)^2$. Hence, in this case, the Hilbert transform is not bounded on $\Lambda_u^p(w)$.

Proof of Theorem 2.1

We will split the proof into several propositions. To prove (a) we need the following lemmas:

Lemma 2.3. *Let $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ and let $\lambda > 0$. Then*

$$(2.4) \quad u(\{x : |H\chi_{(a,b)}(x)| > \lambda\}) = \int_{a-\psi(\lambda)}^{a+\varphi(\lambda)} u(s) ds + \int_{b-\varphi(\lambda)}^{b+\psi(\lambda)} u(s) ds,$$

where

$$\varphi(\lambda) = (b-a) \frac{1}{1+e^{\pi\lambda}} \quad \text{and} \quad \psi(\lambda) = (b-a) \frac{1}{e^{\pi\lambda}-1}.$$

Proof. Since it is known (see [11]) that

$$H\chi_{(a,b)}(x) = \frac{1}{\pi} \log \frac{|x-a|}{|x-b|},$$

the proof follows by easy computations. \square

Lemma 2.4. *Let $0 < p < \infty$. If the Hilbert transform satisfies that*

$$(2.5) \quad \|H\chi_{(0,b)}\|_{\Lambda_u^{p,\infty}(w)} \lesssim \|\chi_{(0,b)}\|_{\Lambda_u^p(w)},$$

for all $b > 0$, then for every $\nu \in (0, 1]$,

$$(2.6) \quad \sup_{b>0} \frac{W\left(\int_{-b\nu}^{b\nu} u(s) ds\right)}{W\left(\int_{-b}^b u(s) ds\right)} \lesssim \left(1 + \log \frac{1}{\nu}\right)^{-p}.$$

Proof. Let $b > 0$. By hypothesis we have that

$$\sup_{\lambda>0} W(u(\{x : |H\chi_{(0,b)}(x)| > \lambda\})) \lambda^p \lesssim W\left(\int_0^b u(s) ds\right),$$

which, applying (2.4), is equivalent to

$$\sup_{\lambda>0} W\left(\int_{-\psi(\lambda)}^{\varphi(\lambda)} u(s) + \int_{b-\varphi(\lambda)}^{b+\psi(\lambda)} u(s) ds\right) \lambda^p \lesssim W\left(\int_0^b u(s) ds\right).$$

Then, we necessarily obtain that, for every $\lambda > 0$,

$$W\left(\int_{\frac{b}{1-e^{\pi\lambda}}}^{\frac{b}{1+e^{\pi\lambda}}} u(s) ds\right) \lambda^p \lesssim W\left(\int_0^b u(s) ds\right).$$

Since $\frac{b}{1-e^{\pi\lambda}} < \frac{-b}{1+e^{\pi\lambda}} < 0 < \frac{b}{1+e^{\pi\lambda}}$, we obtain that

$$W\left(\int_{\frac{-b}{1+e^{\pi\lambda}}}^{\frac{b}{1+e^{\pi\lambda}}} u(s) ds\right) \lambda^p \lesssim W\left(\int_0^b u(s) ds\right).$$

Writing $\nu = \frac{1}{1+e^{\pi\lambda}}$ we get

$$\sup_{b>0} \frac{W\left(\int_{-b\nu}^{b\nu} u(s) ds\right)}{W\left(\int_{-b}^b u(s) ds\right)} \lesssim \left(\log \frac{1-\nu}{\nu}\right)^{-p} \approx \left(1 + \log \frac{1}{\nu}\right)^{-p},$$

for every $\nu \in (0, 1/2)$. On the other hand since, for every $\nu \in (0, 1]$,

$$\sup_{b>0} \frac{W\left(\int_{-b\nu}^{b\nu} u(s) ds\right)}{W\left(\int_{-b}^b u(s) ds\right)} \leq 1,$$

we obtain that (2.6) holds. \square

Remark 2.5. It is known (see [7]) that if the Hardy-Littlewood maximal operator satisfies that $M : \Lambda_u^p(w) \rightarrow \Lambda_u^{p,\infty}(w)$ is bounded, then u is necessarily non-integrable, whereas there are no integrability restrictions on w . However, we shall prove that if the Hilbert transform satisfies (2.4) then both u and w are non-integrable.

If $u = 1$, we recover a well-known result proved by Sawyer in [18], which states that the boundedness of the Hilbert transform on classical Lorentz spaces $H : \Lambda^p(w) \rightarrow \Lambda^p(w)$ implies the non-integrability of w .

As a consequence of the following proposition we obtain the proof of Theorem 2.1 (a).

Proposition 2.6. *If the Hilbert transform satisfies (2.5), then $u \notin L^1(\mathbb{R})$ and $w \notin L^1(\mathbb{R}^+)$.*

Proof. Since w is locally integrable, it is enough to prove that

$$(2.7) \quad W \left(\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} u(x) dx \right) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} W \left(\int_{-t}^t u(x) dx \right) = \infty.$$

Suppose that this limit is a finite number $\ell > 0$. Since, by Lemma 2.4 we have that, there exists $C > 0$ such that, for all $\nu \in (0, 1]$,

$$\sup_{b>0} \frac{W \left(\int_{-b\nu}^{b\nu} u(s) ds \right)}{W \left(\int_{-b}^b u(s) ds \right)} \leq C \left(\log \frac{1}{\nu} \right)^{-p},$$

taking $\nu > 0$ small enough satisfying $C \left(\log \frac{1}{\nu} \right)^{-p} < 1/2$, we obtain that

$$\lim_{b \rightarrow \infty} \frac{W \left(\int_{-\nu b}^{\nu b} u(s) ds \right)}{W \left(\int_{-b}^b u(s) ds \right)} \leq \sup_{b>0} \frac{W \left(\int_{-\nu b}^{\nu b} u(s) ds \right)}{W \left(\int_{-b}^b u(s) ds \right)} \leq \frac{1}{2}.$$

Since we also have that

$$\lim_{b \rightarrow \infty} \frac{W \left(\int_{-\nu b}^{\nu b} u(s) ds \right)}{W \left(\int_{-b}^b u(s) ds \right)} = \frac{\ell}{\ell} = 1,$$

we get a contradiction, and therefore, (2.7) holds. \square

The following proposition gives us as a consequence the proof of Theorem 2.1 (b).

Proposition 2.7. *Let $0 < p < \infty$ and assume that, for every measurable set F ,*

$$\|H\chi_F\|_{\Lambda_u^{p,\infty}(w)} \lesssim \|\chi_F\|_{\Lambda_u^p(w)}.$$

Then, (2.1) holds.

Proof. Let f be a non-negative function supported in I . Let I' be an interval of the same size touching I . If $x \in I'$ we have that

$$|Hf(x)| = \left| \int_{\mathbb{R}} \frac{f(y)}{x-y} dy \right| = \left| \int_I \frac{f(y)}{x-y} dy \right| \geq \frac{1}{2|I|} \int_I f(y) dy.$$

If $f = \chi_E$ with $E \subset I$, and $x \in I'$, then $\frac{|E|}{2|I|} \leq |Hf(x)|$ and hence if $\lambda \leq \frac{|E|}{2|I|}$, we have that $I' \subseteq \{x : |Hf(x)| > \lambda\}$. Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} W(u(I')) &\leq W(u(\{x : |Hf(x)| > \lambda\})) \lesssim \frac{1}{\lambda^p} \int_0^\infty (\chi_E)_u^*(t) w(t) dt \\ &\approx \frac{1}{\lambda^p} W(u(E)). \end{aligned}$$

As the above inequality holds for every $\lambda \leq \frac{|E|}{2|I|}$, we obtain that

$$\frac{W(u(I'))}{W(u(E))} \lesssim \left(\frac{|I|}{|E|} \right)^p.$$

So, it only remains to prove that we can replace I' by the interval I . In fact, the quantities $W(u(I'))$ and $W(u(I))$ are comparable, since taking $E = I$ we get $W(u(I')) \lesssim W(u(I))$, and interchanging the roles of I and I' we get the converse inequality $W(u(I)) \lesssim W(u(I'))$. \square

The proof of Theorem 2.1 (c) is a consequence of (2.1) and it was proved in [7, Lemma 3.3.1].

Proposition 2.8. *Let $0 < p < \infty$ and let us assume that $H : \Lambda_u^p(w) \rightarrow \Lambda_u^{p,\infty}(w)$ is bounded. Then (2.2) holds.*

Proof. Let I and I' be as in Proposition 2.7. Then we have already seen that if f is supported in I , $f_I = \int_I f(x) dx$ and $\lambda \leq \frac{f_I}{2|I|}$, we have that $I' \subseteq \{x : |Hf(x)| > \lambda\}$. Therefore

$$W^{1/p}(u(I')) \leq W^{1/p}(u(\{x : |Hf(x)| > \lambda\})) \leq C \frac{1}{\lambda} \|f\|_{\Lambda_u^p(w)},$$

and since this holds for every $\lambda \leq \frac{f_I}{2|I|}$, we obtain

$$\left(\frac{f_I}{\|f\|_{\Lambda_u^p(w)}} \right) W^{1/p}(u(I')) \lesssim |I|.$$

Considering the supremum over all $f \in \Lambda_u^p(w)$ and taking into account that

$$f_I = \int f(x) (u^{-1}(x) \chi_I(x)) u(x) dx,$$

we get that

$$\|u^{-1} \chi_I\|_{(\Lambda_u^p(w))'} W^{1/p}(u(I')) \lesssim |I|.$$

Since

$$\|\chi_I\|_{\Lambda_u^p(w)}^p = W(u(I)) \leq W(u(3I')) \leq cW(u(I')),$$

we obtain the result. \square

And this concludes the proof of our main Theorem 2.1. Let us now analyze in more detail condition (2.2).

Proposition 2.9.

- i) If $p \leq 1$, condition (2.2) is equivalent to condition (2.1).
ii) If $p > 1$, condition (2.2) is equivalent to the following: for every interval I ,

$$(2.8) \quad \left(\int_0^{u(I)} \left(\frac{\phi_I(t)}{W(t)} \right)^{p'} w(t) dt \right)^{1/p'} \lesssim \frac{|I|}{W^{1/p}(u(I))},$$

where

$$(2.9) \quad \phi_I(t) = \sup\{|E| : E \subset I, u(E) = t\}.$$

Proof. i) If $p \leq 1$, condition (2.2) is equivalent to

$$\|u^{-1}\chi_I\|_{\Gamma_u^{1,\infty}(\tilde{w})} \|\chi_I\|_{\Lambda_u^p(w)} \lesssim |I|,$$

and by Theorem 1.4, we obtain that

$$\sup_{t>0} \frac{\int_0^t (u^{-1}\chi_I)_u^*(s) ds}{W^{1/t}(t)} \lesssim \frac{|I|}{W^{1/p}(u(I))}.$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \sup_{t>0} \frac{\int_0^t (u^{-1}\chi_I)_u^*(s) ds}{W^{1/t}(t)} &= \sup_{t>0} \frac{1}{W^{1/p}(t)} \sup_{u(E)=t} \int_E \chi_I(x) dx \\ &= \sup_{E \subset I} \frac{|E|}{W^{1/p}(u(E))}, \end{aligned}$$

and the result follows.

ii) See Proposition 3.4.4 in [7]. □

Remark 2.10. i) It was proved in [7] that if $u = 1$, (2.8) implies $w \in B_{p,\infty}$ and if $w = 1$, then (2.8) implies $u \in A_p$. In fact, if $w(t) = t^\alpha$ with $\alpha > 0$, then (2.8) also implies $u \in A_p$. To see this, we observe that by hypothesis

$$\left(\int_0^{u(I)} \left(\frac{\phi_I(t)}{t^{\alpha+1}} \right)^{p'} t^\alpha dt \right)^{1/p'} \lesssim \frac{|I|}{u(I)^{(\alpha+1)/p}}.$$

Then, if $\gamma = \alpha(p' - 1)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\int_0^{u(I)} \left(\frac{\phi_I(t)}{t} \right)^{p'} dt \right)^{1/p'} &\lesssim \left(\int_0^{u(I)} \left(\frac{\phi_I(t)}{t} \right)^{p'} \left(\frac{u(I)}{t} \right)^\gamma dt \right)^{1/p'} \\ &= u(I)^{\gamma/p'} \left(\int_0^{u(I)} \left(\frac{\phi_I(t)}{t^{\alpha+1}} \right)^{p'} t^\alpha dt \right)^{1/p'} \lesssim \frac{|I|}{u^{1/p}(I)}, \end{aligned}$$

and hence we obtain the condition for the case $w = 1$ previously studied.

ii) In fact, the above result can be generalized as follows: If $W(t)/t$ is quasi-increasing and $w \in B_\infty^*$, then (2.8) implies $u \in A_p$. To see this we first observe that if $w \in B_\infty^*$ then, for every f decreasing,

$$\int_0^\infty f(s) \frac{W(s)}{s} ds \lesssim \int_0^\infty f(s) w(s) ds$$

and hence

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\int_0^{u(I)} \left(\frac{\phi_I(t)}{t} \right)^{p'} dt \right)^{1/p'} = \left(\int_0^{u(I)} \left(\frac{\phi_I(t)}{t} \right)^{p'} \frac{t}{W(t)} \frac{W(t)}{t} dt \right)^{1/p'} \\ & \lesssim \left(\int_0^{u(I)} \left(\frac{\phi_I(t)}{t} \right)^{p'} \frac{t}{W(t)} w(t) dt \right)^{1/p'} \\ & = \left(\int_0^{u(I)} \left(\frac{\phi_I(t)}{W(t)} \right)^{p'} \left(\frac{W(t)}{t} \right)^{p'-1} w(t) dt \right)^{1/p'} \\ & \lesssim \left(\frac{W(u(I))}{u(I)} \right)^{1/p} \frac{|I|}{W(u(I))^{1/p}} = \frac{|I|}{u(I)^{1/p}}, \end{aligned}$$

from which the result follows.

iii) For every interval I , we have that

$$\phi_I(t) = |I| - \psi_I^{-1}(u(I) - t),$$

where $\psi_I(t) = \sup\{u(F) : F \subset I \text{ and } |F| = t\}$. To see this, we first observe that

$$\phi_I(t) = \sup\{|F| : F \subset [0, |I|] \text{ and } (u\chi_I)^*(F) = t\},$$

where $(u\chi_I)^*(F) = \int_F (u\chi_I)^*(s) ds$. Since $(u\chi_I)^*$ is decreasing we get that the above supremum is attained in a set $F = (a, |I|)$, for some $a > 0$.

Now,

$$t = \int_a^{|I|} (u\chi_I)^*(s) ds = \psi_I(|I|) - \psi_I(a) = u(I) - \psi_I(a)$$

and hence $a = \psi_I^{-1}(u(I) - t)$, from which the result follows.

3. CONSEQUENCES AND APPLICATIONS

As a consequence of (2.2), some necessary conditions on p , depending on w , were obtained in [7]. Following their approach, we see that the same results can be obtained if we assume the boundedness of the

Hilbert transform on weighted Lorentz spaces. First, we need to define the index p_w :

Definition 3.1. Let $0 < p < \infty$. We define

$$p_w = \inf \left\{ p > 0 : \frac{t^p}{W(t)} \in L^{p'-1} \left((0, 1), \frac{dt}{t} \right) \right\},$$

where $p' = \infty$, if $0 < p \leq 1$.

Proposition 3.2. Let $0 < p < \infty$ and assume that $H : \Lambda_u^p(w) \rightarrow \Lambda_u^{p,\infty}(w)$ is bounded. Then $p \geq p_w$. Moreover, if $p_w > 1$ then $p > p_w$.

Proof. See the proof of Theorem 3.4.2 in [7]. \square

Another important consequence of the fact that by Theorem 2.1 (a) we can assume that both u and w are not integrable functions, is that \mathcal{C}_c^∞ is dense in $\Lambda_u^p(w)$ as the following theorem shows:

Theorem 3.3. If $u \notin L^1(\mathbb{R})$, $w \notin L^1(\mathbb{R}^+)$ and $w \in \Delta_2$, then $\mathcal{C}_c^\infty(\mathbb{R})$ is dense in $\Lambda_u^p(w)$.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{S}_c(\mathbb{R})$ be the space of simple functions with compact support and let us note that $\mathcal{S}_c(\mathbb{R})$ is dense in $\Lambda_u^p(w)$. Indeed, by Proposition 1.1 (c), we have that $\mathcal{S}_0(u)$ is dense in $\Lambda_u^p(w)$. On the other hand, given $f \in \mathcal{S}_0(u)$, the sequence $f_n = f\chi_{(-n,n)} \in \mathcal{S}_c(\mathbb{R})$ tends to f pointwise and hence, by Proposition 1.1 (b), it also converges to f in the quasi-norm $\|\cdot\|_{\Lambda_u^p(w)}$.

Now, to prove the density of $\mathcal{C}_c^\infty(\mathbb{R})$ in $\mathcal{S}_c(\mathbb{R})$ with respect to the topology induced by the quasi-norm of $\Lambda_u^p(w)$, it is enough to show that a characteristic function of a bounded measurable set can be approximated by smooth functions of compact support. Thus, let E be a bounded measurable set and let $\varepsilon > 0$. Take a compact set $K \subset \mathbb{R}$ and a bounded open set $U \subset \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$K \subset E \subset U \quad \text{and} \quad u(U \setminus K) \leq \delta,$$

for some small δ to be chosen. Then, by Urysohn's lemma, there exists a function $f \in \mathcal{C}_c^\infty(\mathbb{R})$ such that $f|_K = 1$, $f|_{U^c} = 0$, and $0 \leq f \leq 1$. Then, since $|\chi_E - f| \leq \chi_{U \setminus K}$, we get

$$\|\chi_E - f\|_{\Lambda_u^p(w)}^p \leq \|\chi_{U \setminus K}\|_{\Lambda_u^p(w)}^p = \int_0^{u(U \setminus K)} w(x) dx \leq \int_0^\delta w(x) dx.$$

Therefore, choosing δ small enough we obtain that

$$\|\chi_E - f\|_{\Lambda_u^p(w)} \leq \varepsilon.$$

\square

Remark 3.4. Since H is well defined on functions of $\mathcal{C}_c^\infty(\mathbb{R})$, we deduce by standard methods that the weak-type boundedness of H^* on $\Lambda_u^p(w)$ implies that, for every $f \in \Lambda_u^p(w)$, the limit

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \int_{|x-y|>\varepsilon} \frac{f(y)}{x-y} dy$$

exists almost everywhere.

The third consequence of the previous results is the complete characterization of the weak boundedness of H on $\Lambda_u^p(w)$ in the case $u \in A_1$. We have to mention here that, for the case of the Hardy-Littlewood maximal operator M , it was proved in [7] that

$$M : \Lambda_u^p(w) \rightarrow \Lambda_u^{p,\infty}(w) \iff M : \Lambda^p(w) \rightarrow \Lambda^{p,\infty}(w).$$

The following theorem shows that the same kind of result occurs for H .

Theorem 3.5. *Let $u \in A_1$ and let $0 < p < \infty$. Then*

$$H : \Lambda_u^p(w) \rightarrow \Lambda_u^{p,\infty}(w) \iff w \in B_{p,\infty} \cap B_\infty^*.$$

Proof. Let us start by proving the necessary condition. Since, by Theorem 2.1, (2.2) holds, we can follow the same argument used in [7, Proposition 3.4.4 and Theorem 3.4.8] to conclude that $w \in B_{p,\infty}$. Let us see now that it is also in B_∞^* .

Let $0 < t \leq s < \infty$. Then, since $u \notin L^1(\mathbb{R})$, there exists $\nu \in (0, 1]$ and $b > 0$ such that

$$t = \int_{-b\nu}^{b\nu} u(r) dr \leq \int_{-b}^b u(r) dr = s.$$

By Lemma 2.4 we obtain (2.6) and hence

$$\frac{W(t)}{W(s)} \lesssim \left(1 + \log \frac{1}{\nu}\right)^{-p}.$$

Let $S = (-b\nu, b\nu)$ and $I = (-b, b)$. Since $u \in A_1$, we obtain that

$$\nu = \frac{|S|}{|I|} \lesssim \frac{u(S)}{u(I)} = \frac{t}{s}$$

and therefore

$$\frac{W(t)}{W(s)} \lesssim \left(1 + \log \frac{s}{t}\right)^{-p},$$

From here, it follows that the function

$$\bar{W}(\lambda) = \sup_{s>0} \frac{W(\lambda s)}{W(s)}, \quad 0 < \lambda < 1,$$

is a submultiplicative function satisfying

$$\bar{W}(\lambda) \lesssim \left(1 + \log \frac{1}{\lambda}\right)^{-p}$$

and taking $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $kp > 1$, we obtain that

$$\bar{W}(\lambda) \leq \bar{W}(\lambda^{1/k})^k \lesssim \left(1 + \log \frac{1}{\lambda}\right)^{-kp}.$$

Consequently,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^r \frac{W(t)}{t} dt &\lesssim W(r) \int_0^r \left(1 + \log \frac{r}{t}\right)^{-kp} \frac{dt}{t} \\ &= W(r) \int_1^\infty (1 + \log u)^{-kp} \frac{du}{u} \lesssim W(r), \end{aligned}$$

and hence, by (1.4), $w \in B_\infty^*$.

To prove the converse, we just have to use that if $u \in A_1$, then (see [3, 4]):

$$(3.1) \quad (H^* f)_u^*(t) \leq \frac{1}{t} \int_0^t f_u^*(s) ds + \int_t^\infty f_u^*(s) \frac{ds}{s} := P f_u^*(t) + Q f_u^*(t).$$

whenever the right hand side is finite.

Now, since $w \in B_{p,\infty}$, we have that

$$\sup_{t>0} P f_u^*(t) W(t)^{1/p} \lesssim \|f_u^*\|_{L^p(w)} = \|f\|_{\Lambda_u^p(w)},$$

and the condition $w \in B_\infty^*$ implies the same inequality for the operator Q ; that is (see [1], [16])

$$\sup_{t>0} Q f_u^*(t) W(t)^{1/p} \lesssim \|f\|_{\Lambda_u^p(w)}.$$

Therefore, we obtain that

$$H^* : \Lambda_u^p(w) \rightarrow \Lambda_u^{p,\infty}(w)$$

is bounded and by Fatou's lemma we obtain the result. \square

With a very similar proof and using the properties of the class B_p , the following result is obtained.

Theorem 3.6. *Let $u \in A_1$ and let $1 < p < \infty$. Then*

$$H : \Lambda_u^p(w) \rightarrow \Lambda_u^p(w) \iff w \in B_p \cap B_\infty^*.$$

In the case $p \leq 1$, we obtain the following:

Theorem 3.7. *Let $u \in A_1$ and let $0 < p \leq 1$. Then, if $w \in B_p \cap B_\infty^*$, we have that*

$$H : \Lambda_u^p(w) \rightarrow \Lambda_u^p(w)$$

is bounded.

Remark 3.8. Observe than from the proofs of Theorem 3.5 and 3.6, we also have that, if $u \in A_1$, then

$$H^* : \Lambda_u^p(w) \rightarrow \Lambda_u^{p,\infty}(w) \iff w \in B_{p,\infty} \cap B_\infty^*, \quad p > 0,$$

and

$$H^* : \Lambda_u^p(w) \rightarrow \Lambda_u^p(w) \iff w \in B_p \cap B_\infty^*, \quad p > 1.$$

Our next application concerns the boundedness of H on the Lorentz spaces $L^{p,q}(u)$. In [9], Chung, Hunt, and Kurtz provided a sufficient condition for the boundedness of

$$H : L^{p,1}(u) \rightarrow L^{p,\infty}(u), \quad 1 \leq p < \infty.$$

We prove that this condition is necessary and also complete the characterization of the above boundedness for some other exponents.

Theorem 3.9. *Let $p, r, \in (0, \infty)$, $q, s \in (0, \infty]$.*

- (i) *If $p < 1$ or $p \neq r$, there are no doubling weights u such that $H : L^{p,q}(u) \rightarrow L^{r,s}(u)$ is bounded.*
- (ii) *If $q \leq 1$, the boundedness*

$$H : L^{1,q}(u) \rightarrow L^{1,\infty}(u)$$

holds if and only if $u \in A_1$.

- (iii) *If $q > 1$, the boundedness*

$$H : L^{1,q}(u) \rightarrow L^{1,\infty}(u)$$

does not hold for any u .

Proof. The proofs follow the same ideas of [7, Theorem 3.5.1]:

- (i) Since $L^{r,s}(u) \subset L^{r,\infty}(u)$, if $H : L^{p,q}(u) \rightarrow L^{r,s}(u)$ we would have that $H : L^{p,q}(u) \rightarrow L^{r,\infty}(u)$ is bounded, which is equivalent to have that $H : \Lambda_u^q(t^{q/p-1}) \rightarrow \Lambda_u^{q,\infty}(t^{q/r-1})$ is bounded. Arguing as in Proposition 2.7, we obtain that

$$(3.2) \quad \frac{u^{1/r}(I)}{|I|} \lesssim \frac{u^{1/p}(E)}{|E|}, \quad E \subset I.$$

Then, by the Lebesgue differentiation theorem we get first that $p \geq 1$. On the other hand, if we take $E = I$, then (3.2) implies $u^{1/r-1/p}(I) \lesssim 1$ and hence $p = r$, since $u \notin L^1$ by Theorem 2.1 (a).

- (ii) As before, the boundedness $H : L^{1,q}(u) \rightarrow L^{1,\infty}(u)$ can be rewritten as $H : \Lambda_u^q(t^{q-1}) \rightarrow \Lambda_u^{q,\infty}(t^{q-1})$, and by (2.1) we get

$$\frac{u(I)}{|I|} \lesssim \frac{u(E)}{|E|}, \quad E \subset I,$$

which is equivalent to the condition A_1 . On the other hand if $u \in A_1$ then $H : \Lambda_u^q(t^{q-1}) \rightarrow \Lambda_u^{q,\infty}(t^{q-1})$ holds by Theorem 3.5, taking into account that, since $q \leq 1$, the weight t^{q-1} satisfies the condition $B_{q,\infty} \cap B_\infty^*$.

(iii) If $H : L^{1,q}(u) \rightarrow L^{1,\infty}(u)$ is bounded, we also have the boundedness of $H : L^{1,r}(u) \rightarrow L^{1,\infty}(u)$, $r < 1$ and thus, by (ii), we have that $u \in A_1$. But in this case, Theorem 3.6 asserts that w must be in B_q , while $t^{q-1} \notin B_q$, if $q > 1$. \square

For the case $p > 1$ we finally obtain the following necessary conditions.

Proposition 3.10. *Let $p > 1$ and $0 < q \leq s \leq \infty$. If*

$$H : L^{p,q}(u) \rightarrow L^{p,s}(u)$$

is bounded then:

- (1) *Case $q \leq 1$ and $s = \infty$: $\frac{u(I)}{|I|^p} \lesssim \frac{u(E)}{|E|^p}$, $E \subset I$.*
- (2) *Case $q > 1$ or $s < \infty$: $u \in A_p$.*

Proof. (1) If $q \leq 1$ and $s = \infty$, $H : L^{p,q}(u) \rightarrow L^{p,\infty}(u)$ can be rewritten as $H : \Lambda_u^q(t^{q/p-1}) \rightarrow \Lambda_u^{q,\infty}(t^{q/p-1})$, which by (2.1) implies $\frac{u(I)}{|I|^p} \lesssim \frac{u(E)}{|E|^p}$, $E \subset I$ as we wanted to see.

(2) Let $q > 1$ or $s < \infty$. By (2.2), the boundedness $H : L^{p,q}(u) \rightarrow L^{p,s}(u)$ implies that

$$\|u^{-1}\chi_I\|_{L^{p',q'}(u)}\|\chi_I\|_{L^{p,q}(u)} \lesssim |I|,$$

for all intervals $I \subset \mathbb{R}$. But in [9] it was proved that this agrees with the A_p condition. \square

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